

Research Article

PeriArc: Enhancing Perimeter Measurement through Arc Length Method

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Abstract: This study focuses on improving the accuracy of perimeter measurement for irregular shapes using the Arc Length Method. A user-friendly simulator, PeriArc, is developed to simplify the process and provide a more precise estimation. The method involves deriving a mathematical equation that represents the shape's boundary and then calculating the perimeter by summing the arc lengths of smaller segments. This approach is useful in various fields, including engineering and digital design, where precise measurements are essential. This study focuses on calculating the perimeter of irregular objects which is walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7, Shah Alam. The PeriArc tool makes the process more accessible, even for users without advanced mathematical knowledge. With its potential for real-world applications, this method offers a practical and efficient way to improve perimeter calculations.

Keywords: Arc Length Method; Walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7 Shah Alam

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1. INTRODUCTION

Perimeter is the total length of the boundary surrounding a specific area (Russ et al., n.d.). It represents the continuous outer edge of an object or structure. In geometric terms, perimeter calculation is straightforward for regular shapes such as squares, circles, and triangles. However, in real-world applications, objects often have complex and irregular boundaries, making their perimeter measurement more challenging. (Barrett & Bolt, 2024) The walkways at Tasik Seksyen 7, Shah Alam serve as an example of such irregular structures, where accurate perimeter measurement is essential for urban planning and maintenance.

For irregularly shaped objects, one effective way to determine the perimeter is by breaking the shape into smaller segments and summing their individual lengths. One approach for measuring

curved boundaries is the arc length method, which calculates the precise distance along a curve between two points. This method, derived from calculus, provides an accurate way to determine the perimeter of curved structures. Basic formula or the most popular method to find arc length is by using the radius and angle according to (Grötschel et al., 2022). By applying the arc length method, the total perimeter of the walkways can be estimated by summing the arc lengths of their curved sections (L. Ma, 2020).

This study focuses on the perimeter measurement of the walkways at Tasik Seksyen 7, Shah Alam. Walkways serve as essential pathways for pedestrians, joggers, and cyclists, making their accurate measurement crucial for infrastructure development and maintenance planning. The objective of this research is to determine the estimated perimeter using the arc length method and compare the results with actual measurements to assess the accuracy of this method.

A simulator is a specialized tool that allows users to perform virtual experiments and analyze real-world scenarios based on mathematical models (Chernikova et al., 2020). Simulators are widely used in various fields, including engineering, research, and education, to test hypothesis, optimize designs, and enhance understanding of complex calculations. In mathematical applications, simulators provide an effective way to visualize and analyze mathematical concepts, making computational processes more accessible.

In this project, the PeriArc simulator is developed to estimate the perimeter of the walkways at Tasik Seksyen 7, Shah Alam, using the arc length method. By implementing this approach, PeriArc simplifies the process of measuring irregular perimeters and improves accuracy through structured calculations. The estimated perimeter obtained from the simulator will be compared with actual measurements to evaluate the reliability and effectiveness of this method. The simulator is developed using , ensuring computational efficiency and precision in perimeter calculation.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study involves the following steps:

Step 1: Data Collection

This study computes the arc length of Tasik Seksyen 7's perimeter to enhance measurement accuracy, as shown in figure 1. The image was plotted on a map, as shown in figure 2, and further analyzed using MATLAB, as shown in figure 3. The perimeter of the lake is divided into multiple sections, each represented by simpler curve segments.

Figure 1. Walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7 Shah Alam image

Figure 2. Walkways are plotted on graph paper and divided into segments, where the radius for each length remains same.

Step 2: Perimeter Estimation

This step involves computing the arc length for each curved segment and summing these values to approximate the perimeter of the walkways. This study applies the arc length formula to determine the perimeter more accurately by dividing the boundary into multiple curved sections. Figure 3 displays a section of the PeriArc interface, where users input the segment, radius and angle values into the table. PeriArc calculates the arc length using the formula for each segment and sums the results to estimate the total perimeter.

Figure 3. PeriArc interface

Step 3: Validation and accuracy

The difference between the approximate perimeter calculated using the arc length method in the PeriArc simulator and the manually measured perimeter is used to validate the accuracy of the simulator. To evaluate the effectiveness and reliability of the arc length technique, the percentage relative error is determined using the equation below. The exact perimeter is measured manually using thread and ruler, while the approximate perimeter is computed using the PeriArc simulator.

$$Relative\ Error = \left| \frac{Exact\ value - Approximate\ value}{Exact\ value} \right|$$

Figure 4. Flowchart of PeriArc

3. FINDINGS

This study discusses the use of arc length method to find the perimeter of the walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7 Shah Alam by developing the PeriArc simulator via MATLAB r2023b. Finding the perimeter of walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7 Shah Alam is focus of this study.

3.1 Solution

The map of walkways was plotted and divided into several segments. The calculation can start from any part of the map of walkway.

Figure 5. First interface of PeriArc

Figure 6. User key-in segment, radius and angle and press add to table button to display in the table and total perimeter edit field will compute automatically.

3.2 Result

Table 1. The perimeter for the walkways using PeriArc

Segment	PeriArc Calculation
1	1.3090
2	0.6981
3	0.7854
4	1.3963
5	2.0944
6	1.3090
7	1.3963
8	0.9599
9	2.5307
10	0.6981
11	0.4363
12	0.6109
13	0.3491
14	0.6109
15	2.0071
16	0.8727
17	0.7854
18	0.6109
19	0.6109
20	1.7453
21	1.1345
22	1.0472
23	1.3090
24	1.1345
25	2.0071
26	1.2217
27	0.5236
28	0.6981
29	0.6981
30	0.8727
31	1.7453
32	1.0472
33	0.6981

34	1.7453
35	0.8727
36	1.1345
37	1.3090
38	1.3090
39	1.2217
40	0.8727
41	0.6109
42	0.5236
43	1.1345
44	1.6581
45	2.3562
46	2.7053
47	1.6581
48	0.6109
49	0.7854

Figure 7. The result of perimeter approximation by PeriArc for perimeter of the walkways of Tasik Seksyen 7 Shah Alam.

The result perimeter approximation from PeriArc and manually showing a small difference where PeriArc give the result into 2 decimal places. The perimeter approximation is 56.46 cm and the exact perimeter of the walkways when measured by thread is 58.4 cm. The percentage relative error obtained for this study as follows:

$$\varepsilon\% = \left| \frac{\text{exact value} - \text{approximate value}}{\text{exact value}} \right| \times 100$$
$$\varepsilon\% = \left| \frac{58.4 - 56.46}{58.4} \right| \times 100\% = 3.32\%$$

4. DISCUSSION

The results from PeriArc indicate that PeriArc is the most efficient method for determining perimeter approximation. Manually calculating the perimeter of walkways with multiple curves can be challenging and time-consuming, as each arc length must be computed individually. PeriArc simplifies this process by reducing the workload and providing a fast and efficient way to determine arc length and perimeter approximation.

5. CONCLUSION

Developing a simulator to calculate the perimeter offers numerous advantages across various fields, not just for mathematicians but also for engineers, urban planners, and researchers. Beyond reducing time consumption, the simulator provides a clear visual representation and a user-friendly interface, making it accessible to individuals without advanced mathematical knowledge. Based on the results, the small percentage of relative error indicates that the approximate perimeter calculated using the Arc Length Method closely aligns with the actual perimeter measurements. This confirms that the Arc Length Method is an effective approach for determining the perimeter of irregularly shaped objects, such as walkways. By applying the Arc Length Method, researchers can accurately estimate curved boundaries, ensuring more precise perimeter calculations. This method enables the division of complex shapes into manageable segments, allowing for improved measurement accuracy. Therefore, utilizing a simulator combined with the Arc Length Method proves to be a valuable and reliable strategy for approximating the perimeter of irregularly shaped structures, particularly in real-world applications like urban walkways.

References

- Barrett, D. E., & Bolt, M. D. (2024). Invariant rectification of non-smooth planar curves. *Beitrage Zur Algebra Und* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13366-023-00712-z>
- Chernikova, O., Heitzmann, N., Stadler, M., Holzberger, D., Seidel, T., & Fischer, F. (2020). Simulation based learning in higher education: A Meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(4), 499–541. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320933544>
- Grötschel, M., Hanche-Olsen, H., Holden, H., & Krystek, M. P. (2022). On angular measures in axiomatic euclidean planar geometry. *Measurement Science Review*, 22(4), 152–159. <https://doi.org/10.2478/msr-2022-0019>
- Ma, LKnowing and Teaching Elementary Mathematics: Teachers' Understanding of In. States United the and China in Mathematics Fundamental 5. <https://doi.org/10.4324/978100300944>
- Russ, J. C., Russ, J. C., & Neal, F. B. (n.d.). The Problem of Perimeter.